

Poroelasticity of Hydraulic Fracturing of a Reservoir

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Abstract

The development of numerical simulation of unconventional shale gas reservoirs has been accelerated due to its major contribution in hydrocarbon production. In this study, the developed mode hydro-fractures interact with pre-existing natural fractures and create a fracture network, which later create a fluid flow network, within the reservoir rock. The objective of this study is to simulate the poroelastic response of the rock formation during the extension of fluid flow within the fractures network. It was investigated that the far field poroelastic behavior of the reservoir triggers the rock whether to show elastic or plastic deformation, while the effect of stresses induced fracture propagation is neglected.

1. Introduction

Hydraulic fracturing (or fracking) is the hydraulic stimulation by injecting pressured water into a borehole to increase permeability of the formation. The formation with enhanced permeability is more efficient for hydrocarbon exploitations. During the hydraulic stimulation, tensile stress within the rock matrix may exceed its tensile strength and cause tensile fracture. The resulting tensile fractures (i.e. hydro-fractures) may join to each other and to existing natural fractures and create a network of interconnected fractures. The pore pressure is a key factor in tensile rock fracture. The direction and the extension of fluid flow within the fracture network depend on pore pressure distribution, specifically (Bruno, Dorfmann et al.). The complexity of hydraulic fracturing was addressed by Adachi, Siebrits et al. (2007). In their study, the hydraulic fracturing was noted as a complicated process, which involves three other coupled processes: (i) the rock deformation induced by the pore pressure; (ii) the flow of fluid within the fracture; and (iii) the fracture's mechanical response. Either mechanical response of rock or fracture was modeled using the theory of linear elastic mechanics. The linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) theory provides the conventional energy-release rate approach to define the criterion for fracture propagation. In this literature review, it is noticed that among the numerical studies, the discrete fracture network was not simulated

while it is coupled to the single continuum rock matrix. Therefore, a thorough investigation of poroelastic behavior of the rock formation in response to the fluid flow and its extension within the fracture network was not performed. The deformation of reservoir rock due to the newly developed hydro-fractures was studied by Jacquy, Cacace et al. (2017). The impact of fracture growth on the rock hydraulic properties was addressed in their work, however, no natural fracture was considered. They showed that the diffusive processes and poroelastic effects are responsible for sudden local increase in pore pressure within the matrix. Their results indicated the importance of poroelastic behavior of stimulated reservoir rock.

In this study, the stimulated reservoir volume (SRV) modeling technique is integrated with the finite element approach to simulate a 3-D poroelastic porous matrix coupled with a discrete fracture network. The major objective of this paper is to numerically investigate the rock formation deformation induced fluid flow within the discrete fracture network during the hydraulic fracturing under following assumptions. The SRV is considered to be a typical $100 \times 100 \times 100$ m homogeneous shale rock formation with a centered horizontal wellbore, parallel horizontal plate-like natural fractures, and vertical circular hydro-fractures. The stress field induced fractures growth is neglected due to the enhancement of large scale modeling. Therefore, the hydro-fractures aperture and radius are assumed to remain constant during the transient numerical simulations. However, to investigate the effect of fracture growth on the extension of fluid flow network, different hydro-fractures radius was considered for different models. Each model accounts as an increment of hydraulic fracturing operation.

2. Model Description

The poroelastic response due to the fluid flow extension within a network of hydro-fracture and natural fractures was studied in Barnett Shale, central-eastern Texas, US. The Barnett Shale is the most mature of the currently producing gas shale plays in US (Fan, Luo et al. 2011). This Paleozoic reservoir, located in the Bend Arch Fort

Worth Basin area, is a middle- to late-Mississippian organic-rich shale and discovered to be productive since the early 2000's including (Montgomery, Jarvie et al. 2005, Sone 2012). The thickness of the Barnett Shale varies from 15-30 m in the southwest, up to 300 m in the northeast at the Newark East Field area, (Montgomery, Jarvie et al. 2005). The variation of the viscoelastic properties of Barnett Shale was reported by Sone (2012). The in-situ stress field of the reservoir was stated using the Formation Micro-Imager (FMITM) from a vertical wellbore. The viscoelastic parameters and in-situ stresses of the formation at the depth of ~2600 m are summarized in **Table 1**. Natural fractures were mostly observed at the depth of 2600-2660 m, where the basal hot shale section is located. The strike and dip of the fractures were reported as N50W, 80-85°, respectively (Sone 2012).

Table 1 The viscoelastic parameters and in-situ stresses.

Parameter	Value at depth of ~2600 m
Vertical in-situ stress	65 MPa
Minimum horizontal in-situ stress	47 MPa
Maximum horizontal in-situ stress	85 MPa
Pore pressure	30.5 MPa

In the current study, a horizontal wellbore, was considered within the basal hot shale section of the formation, where the axis of the wellbore is aligned with a horizontal in-situ stress. Either orientation I (*i.e.* perpendicular to wellbore axis) or orientation II (*i.e.* parallel to wellbore axis) of the hydraulic fracture may occur, depending on the direction of the wellbore. Therefore, orientation I occurs when the wellbore axis is parallel to the maximum horizontal in-situ stress (*i.e.* N20E). Orientation II occurs when the wellbore is perpendicular to the maximum horizontal in-situ stress (*i.e.* N110E).

Fig. 1) Hydro-fracture orientation I at depth of 2600-2660 m.

3. Results

The preliminary contours of pressure and hydraulic head at the last propagation increment, shown in **Fig. 2** and **3**, illustrated that the existing natural fractures triggered a path of least resistance to the static pressure that is imposed by intersected hydro fractures. Therefore, new highly permeable regions were accessible to the fluid flow throughout the reservoir.

Fig. 2) Contour of pressure at the last propagation increment.

The fluid flow formed in both vertical plates of hydro fractures as well as horizontal plates of natural fractures. The horizontal flow showed reverse directions at each stage of perforation, thus, created the pressure reinforcement at the vicinity of each hydro fracture.

Fig. 3) Contour of hydraulic head at the last propagation increment.

4. Conclusions

This numerical study was conducted to address the propagation of the hydro fractures in two different orientations. The results of these simulations are presented as one quasi-transient simulation as fracture propagates. The advantage of this method is the

dramatic reduction in computational effort and efficient approach to investigate the growth of fractures. In addition, the system of the natural fracture network (SNFN) was generated in horizontal plates based on laminated and fissile feature of shale gas reservoirs, evidenced in shale outcrops. In the results, the impact of the current realisation of SNFN on the stimulated reservoir volume was evaluated during the interaction of hydro fractures with natural fractures. It was also seen that the natural fractures opening became wider during the hydraulic fracturing. The consequences of opening the horizontal plate-like natural fractures during the hydraulic fracturing were investigated due to poroelastic behaviour of porous matrix. Lastly, a substantial permeability was then created due to the fact that the network of the horizontal plate-like natural fractures became connected via vertical hydro fractures.

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